

Unusual Left Atrial Myxoma Presenting As Horner Syndrome

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Description

The above images are from an elderly patient presenting with left - sided numbness, left eye ptosis and anisocoria, but with normal computed tomography (CT) of the brain; diagnosed with acute Horner syndrome. CT angiography (CTA) of the chest (Figure A) revealed a round left atrial mass measuring 1.5 cm in diameter. Transesophageal echocardiogram (TEE) image revealed a large spherical mass measuring 1.4 x 1.6 cm attached with a thin stalk to the Coumadin ridge (Figure B).

Definity® contrast was administered which revealed enhancement of the periphery of the mass indicative of partial vascularization suggestive of a cardiac tumor (Figures C & D). Surgical resection was successfully performed, and the pathology of the mass confirmed a benign atrial myxoma.

Discussion

Cardiac myxomas are the most common primary benign tumors of the heart, representing about 50% of all cardiac neoplasms [1]. They most frequently arise from the interatrial septum of the left atrium, typically near the fossa ovalis [2]. Rarely, these tumors originate from atypical sites such as the posterior atrial wall, pulmonary vein ostia, or the Coumadin ridge (a muscular ridge located between the left atrial appendage and the left superior pulmonary vein) [3]. Because of their unusual position and potential for mobility, these tumors can mimic other intracardiac masses and present with variable, often misleading, clinical symptoms.

Systemic embolization is a well-documented manifestation of myxomas, with potential to obstruct cerebral, retinal, and peripheral vasculature [4]. However, Horner syndrome, characterized by the triad of ptosis, miosis, and anhidrosis, is an exceptionally rare neurological presentation linked to cardiac myxoma. This syndrome results from disruption of the sympathetic pathway, often due to central embolism or compression of the preganglionic fibers, as happens in cases of carotid dissection or brain stem ischemia [5].

Most cardiac myxomas arise from the interatrial septum, but a minority have been reported from non-septal locations such as the mitral annulus, pulmonary vein orifices, or left atrial appendage [2, 6]. A tumor originating from the Coumadin ridge is exceedingly rare, and the diagnosis is often delayed due to its unusual appearance and proximity to normal anatomical landmarks [3, 7].

Very seldom, cardiac myxomas may manifest with neurological syndromes due to embolic events. In our case, the presentation was Horner syndrome, a constellation of ptosis, miosis, and anhidrosis, caused by disruption of the sympathetic innervation to the eye. The underlying mechanism is most likely tumor embolism affecting the central sympathetic pathway, possibly at the brain stem level or cervical sympathetic chain [8,9].

Only a handful of cases have reported Horner syndrome as the presenting symptom of cardiac tumors, and most of those have been associated with malignant neoplasms or infective emboli [10]. Our case represents a left atrial myxoma with an initial presentation of Horner syndrome. This highlights the embolic potential of even histologically benign tumors and underlines the diagnostic challenge when the neurological presentation antedates overt cardiac symptoms. From a diagnostic standpoint, the location of the tumor on the Coumadin ridge can complicate initial assessment. While chest CT suggested an intracardiac mass, it was transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) that clarified the attachment site and confirmed the suspicion of myxoma. This highlights the importance of imaging modalities in differentiating myxomas from thrombus, ridge hypertrophy, or papillary fibroelastomas, particularly in unusual locations. In our case, the initial differential diagnosis included left atrial thrombus or myxoma, both of which may appear as echogenic mobile masses near the left atrial appendage.

Given the diagnostic uncertainty, contrast-enhanced echocardiography using Definity® (perflutren lipid microspheres) was employed to characterize the mass. Definity® contrast agents enhance the delineation of endocardial borders

and improve mass characterization by demonstrating vascularity within a lesion [11]. Myxomas, being vascularized tumors, typically show contrast enhancement, whereas thrombi are avascular and do not enhance [12].

In our case, contrast opacification of the mass was observed, favoring the diagnosis of myxoma over thrombus. This was later confirmed by surgical histopathology. The use of Definity® contrast played a crucial role in non-invasively differentiating tumor from thrombus, especially given the tumor's unusual location on the Coumadin ridge, where anatomical variants can lead to misinterpretation.

In recent years, contrast echocardiography has emerged as a valuable adjunct to standard imaging for evaluating intracardiac masses, particularly in patients with suboptimal acoustic windows or equivocal findings on standard transthoracic echocardiography [13]. Its real-time application, accessibility, and safety profile make it an excellent first-line tool, especially when advanced imaging such as MRI may be delayed or contraindicated. Thus, in patients presenting with atypical left atrial masses, especially near the left atrial appendage or pulmonary vein ostia, contrast-enhanced echocardiography should be considered to improve diagnostic accuracy and facilitate early surgical planning.

Surgical excision remains curative and is strongly indicated given the risk of further embolization or obstruction. In our case, the mass was resected with preservation of adjacent structures, and histopathology confirmed a classic myxoma lesion.

Conclusions

This case underscores the diagnostic challenges posed by cardiac myxomas in atypical locations, such as the Coumadin ridge, and their potential to present with rare neurological symptoms like Horner syndrome due to embolic phenomena. It highlights the critical role of advanced imaging particularly contrast-enhanced echocardiography in distinguishing myxomas from other intracardiac masses. Early recognition and surgical excision remain

essential to prevent further embolic complications and ensure favorable outcomes.

Manuscript submitted Sept 21, accepted Sept 28, 2025

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<https://cardiofellows.com/newsletter-september-2025.html>

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KEYWORDS: Left Atrial Appendage; Cardiac Tumors; Stroke; Horner Syndrome; Large Atrial Myxoma.

Reference this article as:

Mumtaz M, Makwana K, Talha M, Kaur K, Ahsan M, Khan S, Omar B. Unusual Left Atrial Myxoma Presenting As Horner Syndrome. *Cardiofel Newslet* 2025. Sept; 8(9):18 – 21.